



Stickers for your snowboard are cool. Free stickers in the mail are even cooler. Stickers are a must-have, but not everyone wants to spend money on them. How can you get stickers free of charge for your snowboard? This is possible with several simple and easy methods.

It is easiest to have someone just give you a sticker. If you're at a snowboard event such as the US Open, or the X-Games, this is unlikely to happen. Vendors at these events are hungry for people to take their stickers so they give them to anyone who asks or is walking by their booth.

Another option is to be lucky and buy a product. If the company is smart enough, they will often include stickers when you purchase snowboard equipment. However, this is not always possible. Some products aren't available online so they won't ship them to you so you don't get the stickers that you want. You can think [check that](#) of energy drinks such as Monster or Rock Star. Their stickers are some of the best and I have never been offered a free sticker when I bought a Monster energy drink at my local Quickie Mart.

Another option is to ask for stickers at a Zumiez-certified retailer. They usually have a ton just sitting around taking up space so they might as well be on your board.

The problem remains however. How can I get free stickers in the mail?

The easiest way that requires the least amount of effort that I know of is to contact the companies directly. It is totally free and can even be done while you sit on your couch and watch Robot Chicken reruns too. You have the option to call, write, or fill out their contact form online. You can pick and choose which companies to contact which requires you to hunt down email addresses and sort through all of the website mumbo-jumbo to find the snail mail info or contact form. The easiest option is to find a website or forum that has a list of this information already compiled for you. Then you just pick and choose which company to contact for your free stickers.

It isn't a perfect system, as not all companies will give you the stickers free of charge. However, many will. The ones who don't will usually want you to send a self-addressed stamped envelope to them (so they don't have to pay postage) and then you'll get your stickers. Some people require you to send money, usually one or two dollars. You can decide how much effort and time you want to put into getting your stickers. However, a few stickers sent in the mail is well worth it.